

Marginalisation, Memory and the Notion of Caste: A Select Study of Dalit Autobiographies

**Dr. Subhendu Dutta,
Independent Researcher,
Assam, India.**

Abstract: Dalits occupy the lowest position in the Indian society. They are also called untouchables and outcastes. They are crushed, oppressed and traumatised by the traditional caste system that continues to divide India into higher castes and lower castes on the basis of purity and pollution. Dalits continue to struggle in this postcolonial world where the stigma of untouchability compels them to occupy the lowest position. The bane of untouchability acts as an adamant barrier that prevents every Dalit from bathing, eating, drinking and worshipping with the upper castes who crush them. While Dalit men struggle against caste, Dalit women find themselves in a situation that is far more challenging because they are victimised by the upper class as well as by members of their own community. This leads to the double marginalisation of Dalit women. At present, Dalits have become conscious of their lowly position within the social sphere. This realization gets projected by the emergence of Dalit literature that critiques the tenets of the caste system. This paper, through a close reading of Namdeo Nimgade's *In The Tiger's Shadow* (2010) and Urmla Pawar's *The Weave of My Life* (2008) makes an attempt to understand the impact of the caste system on the existence of Dalits-their experiences and position at the bottom of the caste hierarchy. It looks into the process of writing personal narratives where a complex picture of the marginalised Dalit community gets documented with the active help of memory.

Keywords: Double Marginalisation, Caste hierarchy, Untouchability, Oppressed, Memory, Dalit literature, Outcastes

The unfair practice of the Hindu caste system has left an indelible mark of pain and trauma upon the Dalit community. The pangs of division and social inequality have ruined the Dalits in every way. There are “ineradicable legacies of violent histories through generations” (Schwab 1) that haunt and traumatise the Dalit psyche which opens up through memoirs and autobiographies. Dalit autobiographies are narratives of the most beleaguered members who constantly struggle for basic rights. The ironclad rule of the Hindu caste system robs them of their personal freedom by denying their right to work, education and adequate health care in a civil sphere which is shared by both victims and perpetrators who consider them as untouchables:

Untouchability, an ancient form of discrimination based upon caste, is a complex and pervasive problem within India, although its practice is not limited to India alone. For millennia, the practice of untouchability has marginalized, terrorized, and relegated a section of Indian society to a life marked by violence, humiliation and indignity. The discrimination is so pervasive that many Dalits come to believe that they are responsible for their own suffering and exclusion, internalizing the beliefs that perpetuate the practice of untouchability. (Jammanna and Sudhakar 29)

Dalit autobiographies aptly portray this sad scenario of Dalits who are maimed on the basis of purity and pollution. They remain faceless and voiceless because the caste system continues to thrive

and break the backbone of their community by inflicting verbal and physical abuse on their soul that declares:

...Dalit means broken. Broken by suffering. Broken by caste: the world's oldest, longest-running dominator system, decreed in scriptures and enforced by unspeakable acts of violence. Broken by the horror of the enormity of human potential that was lost to this violent system-lives not fully lived, and souls who never got to sing their full song. (Soundararajan 2)

The genre of autobiography has always been a favorite medium of expression for individuals who come from different fields. It is a literary form that “involves the reconstruction of the movement of a life, or part of a life, in the actual circumstances in which it was lived” and “its centre of interest is the self” (Roy 9) whose journey is presented through a series of episodes. In India, the tradition of autobiographies began with Banarasidas's *Ardhakathanaka* (1641). This was followed by other prominent writers who chose the medium of autobiography to showcase their individual achievements. Thus the genre of autobiography slowly emerged as a major trend and it has been observed that:

Indian autobiographies are written by persons coming from different and divergent fields of politicians, social workers, philosophers, civil servants, public figures and others. While the autobiographies written by men outnumbered women's autobiographies, nevertheless Indian women had a dictinction in narrating their personal-life stories in as early as second part of the nineteenth century...Dalits, on the other hand, have started narrating their life-stories only

after independence because education was denied to them for quite a long time. (Kumar 43)

Independent India gave the Dalits some respite from the brutality of the caste system as it made education free and compulsory for all. The power of education enabled them to understand the precarious nature of their existence within the civil sphere. The new educated Dalits emerged as a class that was able to articulate their position as victims of marginalisation and subordination through their personal narratives. The caste system that has resulted in the social stratification of the Indian society continues to challenge the values of our civilization as it imposes a series of restrictions on the lower castes who are given the status of untouchables on the basis of *Manusmriti* that served the interests of the upper caste. Dalit autobiographies like Namdeo Nimgade's *In the Tiger's Shadow* (2010), Urmila Pawar's *The Weave of My Life* (2008) and Baby Kamble's *Jina Amucha* or *The Prisons We Broke* (2008) critique this particular aspect of the civil sphere where the life of every Dalit remains under the shadow of hatred and aggression.

Individuals like Nimgade and Pawar get marginalised by the caste system that compels them to remain in the periphery or the margins. Marginalisation, as observed by Young, stands as the most dangerous form of oppression because it excludes Dalits from social and economic spheres and pushes them “into an environment that offers less chance of leading a healthy and fulfilled life” (Stretch 313). Nimgade's narrative is a record of the torture inflicted on Dalits who lives get overshadowed by centuries of slavery and oppression. The life of Nimgade and Dalits like him is a stark reminder of the chaturvarnic order that compels the Dalit community to remain in the periphery or the

margins. This becomes clear when Nimgade describes the pathetic existence of his Mahar community:

“...In the village we untouchables lived apart from the others according to the old saying, Mahar anhi gaon che bahar (Mahars should remain outside the village). We could not even enter the yard of high-caste houses- especially in the morning, after they purified their yards with a sprinkling of gobar (cowdung) in water” (*Tiger’s Shadow* 40).

This short description presents “the caste mentality” which is “based on categorical differences” and “can promote inequality, xenophobia, prejudice, and racism (Weiss 120). The text by Nimgade is filled with such descriptions that bring to light the marginal self of the Dalits. A close reading of the text reveals that the entire autobiography is a record of Nimgade’s pain and sufferings. There are six parts that vehemently satirize the caste system that continues as an age-old Indian tradition. In Part I, we are told about his family of bonded labourers that lives in an area which is surrounded by jungles: “This was in the remote village of Sathgaon in the state of Maharashtra, 500 miles- and a universe away- from what was then Bombay... The landscape could change dramatically, from a rich green during monsoons, to dusty parched land during droughts that deprived us of food and water” and “there was no hospital, post office or paved road” (*Tiger’s Shadow* 4). This was Nimgade’s small world that was remote, unsafe and humiliating and he shared it with his seven siblings. They also had the burden of age-old tradition that compelled them to run barefoot in front of bullock carts owned by the upper caste members and eat their leftovers:

It was because of the curse of untouchability that we had to compete with animals. This was but one of the several inhuman and very painful but “necessary” social rituals devolving from chaturvarna, the Hindu code that created the caste system. (*Tiger’s Shadow* 16).

The school was one more place where Nimgade felt the curse of the caste- convention. His caste became his status marker and thwarted his attempts to achieve a sense of identity against caste oppression: “The Headmaster admitted me under the strict condition that I, being untouchable, must never enter the schoolhouse. Instead, I should have to stand outside with a handful of other untouchables on the hot verandah and listen to lesson through a window (*Tiger’s Shadow* 27-28). Fortunately, Nimgade was able to overcome all these obstacles. He was hard-working and in Part II, we meet Nimgade with his B.Sc degree. The Banaras Hindu University became his next destination and then he joined the Indian Agricultural Research Institute. Nimgade’s eventful life is an example of an individual’s journey from the periphery to the centre. He is determined and makes efforts to repair his social conditions. The text reflects his philosophy which states: “one should try to follow ones’s decisions, in dealing with hardships, and to listen to ones’s gut feelings and intuitions. One needs to use common sense, and listen to what one’s inner advice tells him or her to do... (Dobrovidel 220). The text is indeed a long journey undertaken by Nimgade to show an individual’s protest against injustice arising out of the caste system that denies the equality of men. At the end, we find a proud Nimgade showing his caste identity to a guard guarding India’s Bhabha Atomic Research Centre:

I raised my right hand in the air and pulled up my shirtsleeve. There on my forearm was the now blurred tattoo from my childhood in the village. Next to the figure of a Hindu God was my name, “Namdeo Maratrao Nimgade.”

The guard was astonished. ‘Sir.’ He said. You are evidently a highly educated scientist, but you have this tattoo-the mark of a lowly village beginning! How can that be?

I related to him my story in a few minutes, essentially a synopsis of this book, about how a poor and illiterate untouchable could leave the bonds and shackles of poverty and discrimination by following the path of Dr. Ambedkar. *Tathagat. Jai Bhim!* (*Tiger’s Shadow* 288).

The text that comes next is Urmila Pawar’s *The Weave of My Life* (2008). It depicts the predicament of Dalit women who have been marginalised by the caste-system that represents the “brahmanical patriarchy” (Chakraborty 78). She is also a victim of domestic violence committed by the Dalit man who uses her as his punching bag. The Dalit woman has to face the bane of untouchability and at the same time carry the burden of traditions of her community. She is forced to humbly submit and internalize their lowly status as objects of sexual gratification. She has to follow the dictations of patriarchy and silently suffer the attack of Hindu scripts and religious institutions that celebrate gender inequality. Thus, Dr. (Mr) Shibu Simon and Mr. Sijo Varghese C present a shocking picture when they describe her as:

The eternal other, the perpetual minor, an occasional and incomplete being. A kind of imperfect man-a woman is everything but a person...At the lowest caste level, a

wretched landscape presents itself: Dalit women are paraded naked, raped; her children and husband are forced to drink urine; she is made to carry shit on her head and told to force it down her throat too. She is ostracized. She is prostituted; her sexuality is religion's playground. Even Dalit men have debased her to a level lower than where they find themselves in; from where they are crying for emancipation. (240).

This clearly indicates the plight of Dalit women who have been doubly marginalised by the patriarchal order that holds women as an inferior entity or the 'other.' Individuals like Manu has compared woman and the lower castes as agents who must show unquestioning obedience and perform their duties within the social sphere. The "androcentric assumptions" made by Freud paint a similar picture where a man stands as a "normal human" while his female counterpart is "a deviant human being lacking a penis, whose entire psychological structure" constantly struggles "to compensate for this deficiency" (Lerner 19,21). Dalit women writers like Kamle and Pawar have challenged these lopsided observations made on woman and they have used the medium of autobiography to firmly assert their identity as individuals who have the power to resist, question and critique the tenets of patriarchy that govern social, political and economic spheres. By doing so, these writers have broken the age-old tradition that visualizes woman as a passive creature who must humbly submit to the pressures of household chores bear the responsibility of motherhood. The act of writing one's autobiography is an attempt that enables an individual to embark on a journey of self discovery because:

Writing about oneself is a conscious act as it represents the subject's desire to express-and thus record-feelings and

emotions, as well as events. Though an individual diarist may start writing initially at random, the fact that the momentum is sustained over a period of time implies that the act of writing is fulfilling a certain role. It helps in the formation of a distinct identity and of a sense of self, as the writer is able to physically view on palm leaves or paper what she feels about herself. Often it can be followed by a period of reflection, observation and even recantation. Out of all this, a being emerges, a creation often of fractured, disjointed accounts of life, which do not always follow a chronological pattern. Sometimes, this self expression comes at a specific time of life when, due to a number of reasons, opportunities coincide with the desire to write. (Karlekar 15-16)

The Weave of My Life (2008) is a quintessential example of this process. The text presents Dalit women as victims of double oppression- “by the upper caste men as well as by the men of their own community. Their struggle is, on the one hand, for existence and on the other, to protect themselves against the hostile social environment. This hostility pervades all spheres-at home as well as outside (Kumar 6). Pawar’s narrative takes us to the rugged Konkan coast where she grew up as a child. As a Dalit girl, she was always under the pressure of caste, patriarchy and various other Dalit traditions. The caste hierarchy placed her at the bottom and made her existence obscure. She lived in a world where justice, dignity and social status were totally absent, Her caste identity labeled her as a Mahar Dalit and she belonged to a community that was weak and struggled with the unjust notion of pollution that was always attached to its existence:

...the Mahar community could be summoned anytime by the upper castes, or could be attacked from all sides if anything went wrong. They were supposed to work hard during the preparations of festivals like Holi but they were not entitled to participate in it like the upper castes. If they tried to do so they were beaten up till they bled (*weave of My Life* xvi-xvii)

Such occasional assaults were like wounds that fractured their social status and compelled them to internalize the tyranny of the upper castes in complete silence. They were like animals who had to obey and then slowly perish like insects. Achille Mbembe presents a similar portrait of the African natives who were considered inferior and useless by the West that still describes Africa as a place “that is incomplete, mutilated, and unfinished (Mbembe 1).

Pawar grew up in a family that was poor. She lost her dad when she was in the third standard. Fortunately her mother was there to support her studies. Like Nimgade, she too was a victim of caste politics that made her childhood traumatic. Her teacher, Kerlekar Guruji terrorized her because she was a Dalit. He slapped her because he thought that their cow Kapila had made the class dirty. Pawar was asked to clean Kapila’s dung and when she refused, she was severely punished. Her swollen cheeks were enough to trigger her mother’s anger who immediately rushed to the school and demanded for justice:

My girl studies in your class, Guruji! What did she do today that you beat her up so much? She pulled me towards him and showed him my swollen cheek. ‘Your white cow shits in the verandah.’ ‘Our white cow ? She shits there,

eh? Why, did you see her doing that? Look, I am a widow; my life is ruined. Yet I sit here, under this tree and work. Why? Because I want education for my children so that their future will be better...(*Weave of My Life* 68-69)

Pawar's classmates were equally offensive and brutal Her sad recollections of the school picnic serves as a shocking incident in which Pawar lost her self dignity. The recollections of Baby Kamble in her autobiography are similar: "A majority of girls in our class belonged to the higher castes. For the first time in their lives, they had girls like us- who could pollute them-studying with them. They treated us like lepers, as if our bodies dripped with dirty blood or as if pus oozed out of our rotten flesh (*Prisons We Broke* 108). Thus, poverty and humiliation come together to haunt every Dalit. Pawar, too, was a leper who was allowed to join the picnic but was also told not to touch anything:

They did not allow me to touch anything though we all ate together. I really enjoyed the meal. The next day I was horrified to hear that my eating had become the hottest topic for juicy gossip. Girls were whispering in groups about how I had eaten, 'She ate like a monster,' someone said. Another endorsed it, 'God she ate like a goat,' She ate so much of everything! Awful! It was so humiliating that I died a thousand deaths that day! (*Weave of My Life* 102)

Such deaths are psychological in nature because they kill your inner peace. Both Kamble and Pawar have experienced it along with their community. Bama is one more towering figure among Dalits who narrates another startling tale of oppression. She became a Christian but her religious conversion did not improve her status as a Dalit. She became a catholic nun and later realized

that the new religious order had members from the upper caste who were uncooperative and critical about Dalit Christians like her. Later Bama resigned and returned to her community life where she witnessed a life “without a paisa in one’s hand” (*Karukku* 102-103). Bama’s *Karukku* (1992) records all these incidents in spoken Dalit Tamil and this was a deliberate attempt to challenge the standardized written Tamil that carried the signature of the upper caste writers in Tamil Nadu:

Bama’s conscious choice of spoken Dalit Tamil, ungoverned by the tyranny of elaborate grammatical rules, as a medium to voice the story of her community is indeed instructive. In a spirit of defiance, it obviously challenges the authority of literacy over orality, a divide which was ratified and nourished by Tamil Shaivism or Tamil nationalism of different hues, including mainstream Dravidianism during this century. But at an equally important plane, it is an effort by Bama to break free from her proficiency in standardized written Tamil, a result of her privileged education in schools and colleges, and to lose herself in the community of Dalits. (Pandian 132-133)

Urmila Pawar creates a similar landscape which has a “regional flavor” by using words like “aai” (mother), “kaka” (uncle), “nanand”(husband’s sister), “sasu”(mother-in-law), “vahini” (brother’s wife) etc. Thus she “uses the vocabulary with its raw usage which becomes illustrative of her silent voice” and establishes her “connection closer” to her Maher community. Her confessional mode of narrating her relationship with her husband, Harishchandra, is one more interesting aspect of her unique style that reminds us of Kamala Das. Pawar’s husband was a typical Dalit man who tried to dominate her and was not at all happy with

his wife's educational qualifications. Her progress bruised her "husband's ego" who slowly moved away from her (Singh and Rauthan 28). Pawar was also blamed for her husband's illness and failed ventures:

Even in his last days, I got squarely blamed for Harishchandra's illness. First it was said that he was completely heartbroken by his daughter's rebellious marriage. Gradually, my education, my job, my writing, my social work, my meetings, my programmes and finally I, because of what I was, were held responsible for his illness. But nothing affected me anymore! Nothing! Neither Harishchandra's harsh words, nor his tantrums, nor our fights! All that I was able to see was a great wave of darkness, pitch-black as coal powder, rolling towards Harishchandra who faced it with his back turned to me...
(*Weave of My Life* 317)

As a man, Harishchandra could not appreciate Pawar who was constantly criticized for asserting herself as a symbol of courage and determination. Urmila's husband expected her to be like the "village woman whom he had seen in his youth" but she was not ready to submit to the "archaic gender rules" that gave rise to domestic violence and tightened the "patriarchal hold on women's lives" (*Weave of My Life* xx-xxi). This shows the physical and psychological struggle that a Dalit woman has to face in both the public and private domains. She is like a dumb animal that gets tormented and abused by the patrons of Dalit patriarchy and the ideology of caste system:

In those days, at least one woman in a hundred would have let her nose chopped off. You may well ask why. It's

because of the sasu, who would poison her son's mind. These sasus ruined the lives of innocent women forever. Every day the Maharwada would rebound with the cries of some hapless women in some house or the other. Husbands flogging their wives, as if they were beasts, would do until the sticks broke with the effort. The heads of these women would break open, their backbones would be crushed, and some would collapse unconscious. But there was nobody to care for them. (*Prisons We Broke* 98)

The narratives of both Kamle and Pawar aptly portray this physical abuse and psychological trauma of Dalit women who face “triple exploitation” of “caste, class and gender.” Their stories “unlike the Dalit male narratives, are more inward looking” as they not only “interrogate the evil practices of Dalit community” but also highlight the tensions that exist between the upper caste men and the Dalits (*Prisons We Broke* 160-163). Their texts can be considered as an “act of a conscious self which is documented through the active help of memory’ (Kumar 3). Their texts narrate the miserable plight of an entire community that continues to suffer the religious sanctions of the caste system designed to champion the hegemony of the upper castes.

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